

Development of Real-Time Image Processing Frameworks for Smart Traffic Systems

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ABSTRACT

Real-time image processing frameworks are very important for developing intelligent traffic systems, ensuring effective traffic monitoring and incident detection with prompt decision support. The systems are critical in advancing urban mobility, reducing congestion, and ensuring safety. In this paper, a Hybrid GAN and ViT Model has been proposed to handle some of the challenges related to real-time classification of traffic events related to accidents, variable traffic conditions, and fire incidents. This hybrid model GAN-ViT combines the strong generative powers of Generative Adversarial Networks with spatial feature extraction expertise of Vision Transformers. Accuracy and F1-score were also found to be 98.63% and 98.43%, respectively, when validated on the TrafficNet dataset. Ongoing advancements in real-time applications are being called for because detection of traffic events is urgently needed quickly and accurately. It thus offers an effective, high-performance method for classifying traffic events in intelligent traffic systems that are advancing towards future transportation. This proposed model has the potential to transform traffic management by enabling faster and more accurate event detection, which is crucial for effective emergency response and comprehensive traffic optimization. It emerged as the new practice of state-of-the-art advanced transformer-based architectures along with generative models for improving the efficiency of traffic monitoring systems.

Keywords: *Intelligent Traffic Management and Control (ITMC), Deep Learning (DL), Traffic congestion, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Vision Transformers (ViTs), Urban Mobility.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The problems caused by urbanization are becoming more complex as cities all over the world are transforming into linked centers of creativity and technology. Congestion is a major problem in this densely populated area, lowering productivity, damaging the environment, and lowering people's quality of life[1][2]. Increases in both the number of people living in cities and the number of vehicles on the road put a pressure on our transportation networks that can only be met with creative solutions. The emergence of "smart cities," characterized by the widespread adoption of cutting-edge technological solutions, offers a once-in-a-generation chance to implement intelligent transportation systems that may alleviate the many negative effects of traffic jams[3].

With the rise of intelligent traffic management and control (ITMC) systems, researchers have been working on ways to make them more precise, efficient, and successful in traffic management solutions. Two primary features that are included into ITMC are the forecasting of traffic states and the regulation of junction signals. There are typically two types of approaches to traffic flow analysis. One kind relies on statistical techniques and data-driven methodologies to generate hypotheses and assumptions at both the macro and micro levels. But these methods aren't up to the task of dealing with complicated road configurations and unpredictable traffic[4].

The rapid increase in urbanization has made traffic congestion a serious problem in cities throughout the globe. The quality of life for local residents may be drastically diminished and economic losses might occur as a consequence of traffic congestion. Traffic congestion occurs from increased vehicles, poor management, population growth, inadequate infrastructure, accidents, construction, parking issues, and car dependence. Addressing these requires improved infrastructure, prioritizing public transport, carpooling, and cycling, Invest in smart traffic management, robust infrastructure, and endorse flexible work hours [5]. The concept of "smart cities" has emerged as a potential solution to this problem; these urban areas would maximize the operation of many city services, including transportation, by using state-of-the-art technologies like the IoT, AI, and ML. One of the primary challenges in smart city traffic flow optimization is the accurate prediction of traffic congestion. It is

possible to alter traffic signals or reroute vehicles in order to avoid or reduce congestion with the help of accurate traffic jam forecasts[6].

Because it promotes economic growth and road user comfort, traffic flow is crucial to a nation's development[7][8]. Because the transportation industry is growing, traffic information authorities are focusing more on monitoring traffic volume. Forecasts of traffic allow officials to allocate resources in advance to guarantee a smooth trip. Congestion limits the utility of street networks. The community bears direct and indirect expenses as a consequence of the cutbacks[9]. Numerous studies have examined the impact of traffic on the social structure and economic system. Traffic congestion is the primary cause of late working hours. Later calculations showed that traffic and congestion cost the US economy 8.8 billion work hours annually. The issue of traffic prediction is the estimation of traffic level characteristics, using a number of AI approaches and the collected traffic data, for example, those that are fifteen minutes to several hours long. Trip duration, occupancy, congestion rate, traffic volume, as well as traffic volume are the five criteria that are often taken into account while measuring and forecasting congestion. The overload parameters are evaluated using a variety of AI approaches, each tailored to the specific kind of data collected[10][11]. Nevertheless, a significant quantity of time series data is needed for a model to work well, and the model's effectiveness mostly depends on how well it can represent the geographical and temporal characteristics of the traffic conditions. Furthermore, models struggle with missing or corrupted data, which reduces their ability to provide accurate and relevant predicting results.

Recently, there has been a lot of focus on developing methods to predict when traffic would be heavy, particularly in the fields of artificial intelligence and machine learning. Due to the quantity of data from probing navigation systems or static sensors, this field of research has developed substantially during the previous few decades[12]. To predict traffic congestion, especially temporary congestion issues, a number of traffic variables are assessed. Most research on traffic congestion prediction uses historical data. However, several articles have made real-time predictions of congestion issues. From a modifiability point of view, forecasting traffic congestion is a more challenging task than predicting traffic flow in non-congested situations. An alarm system enables traffic controllers to put relief measures into action. The infrastructure for gathering traffic statistics has become better over time. Thanks to this development and the increase in computing power, researchers may now employ deep neural network (DNN) predictions for transportation [13].

To take advantage of these benefits, earlier methods used ML or empirical algorithms to predict incoming traffic. By way of algorithms that are based on characteristics gathered and real-time traffic data, they reveal and keep fundamental traffic conditions up to date using qualities that are built by humans. Environmental considerations, traffic limits, and other such factors may, in fact, affect incoming traffic. It has been shown that these separately selected characteristics are insufficient to adequately describe traffic data, which prevents an accurate forecast. Recent advances in deep learning (DL) theory have been facilitated by the availability of massive amounts of data and the ease with which it can be processed. The remarkable feature extraction capabilities of DL from massive amounts of source data have garnered a lot of interest. Several areas have already put it to good use, including voice and object recognition.

By using a multi-layer structure, DL models have been able to uncover fascinating patterns and nonlinearities, in contrast to classic ML models such as SVM and ANN, which rely on a shallow infrastructure to gather data. By collecting features from different angles, layers allow for a multi-level abstraction[14]. Integrating DL with comprehensive mobility data has the potential to improve future traffic estimates via its widespread usage and influence. By contrasting them with more conventional statistical approaches, this research delves into the revolutionary possibilities of state-of-the-art real-time image-processing frameworks as well as DL technologies in ITMC. Although statistical methods have traditionally shed light on traffic trends and patterns, they aren't always flexible and precise enough for use in complicated real-time settings. The novelty lies in empirically demonstrating how these deep-learning models surpass statistical methods in accuracy, scalability, and robustness, ultimately reshaping the ITMC landscape.

Real-time image processing frameworks are an integral part of developing the capabilities of Intelligent Traffic Management and Control systems. These can capture live traffic data by making use of high-resolution cameras along with advanced computer vision algorithms and detect congestion, accidents, or irregularities in real time.

This will be able to make dynamic decisions in traffic control by adjusting signal timings, rerouting traffic, or alerting the authorities. Using deep learning models, real-time visual processing may enhance traffic forecast accuracy and enables quicker responses to unpredictable traffic patterns, offering a more adaptive and efficient approach to managing urban mobility.

1.1. Contribution of The Research

- Develops a hybrid deep-learning framework combining Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) for image enhancement and Vision Transformers (ViTs) for precise traffic pattern recognition, enabling scalable and real-time ITMC solutions.
- Utilizes advanced image processing techniques for traffic image enhancement, improving object detection and recognition in challenging conditions such as low-light, rain, or fog.
- Demonstrates the superior accuracy and performance of deep learning models over traditional statistical methods in handling complex traffic scenarios, including dynamic traffic densities and varying weather conditions.
- Facilitates real-time traffic monitoring and forecasting, improving the efficiency of traffic control systems and supporting urban planning efforts to reduce congestion.

Here are the following sections: In Section 2, we survey the existing literature on the topic of traffic congestion prediction using deep learning methods, highlighting knowledge gaps in the field. Section 3 will provide background information on the proposed models, which are GAN and ViT. The approach for data collection and preprocessing, model designs, and assessment techniques are described in Section 4. Results are presented, performance measures are discussed, and the efficacy of the suggested models is compared in Section 5. Section 6 provides a review of the key findings as well as suggestions for future research, concluding the study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent research on real-time image processing and traffic control systems is included in Table 1. It offers a summary of the approaches, data sets, important discoveries, and observations from several studies that have aided in the creation of sophisticated traffic forecast, control, and incident detection systems. Every study emphasizes the suggested methods, findings, and possible directions for more research or development in the subject of intelligent traffic systems.

Table 1 Previous Works Real-Time Image Processing Frameworks for Smart Traffic Systems

Sr. No	Purpose	Methodology	Dataset	Findings	Remark	Ref
1	To present an architecture for a smart traffic light system that continuously analyzes the traffic situation and adjusts the lights appropriately.	YOLO (You Only Look Once) is used to propose a vision-based DTLS approach.	This study uses the COCO dataset, which has 3,30,000 pictures in 80 distinct classifications.	Reduced traffic delays; prioritized traffic in schools, hospitals, and workplaces; built emergency vehicle green lanes	Improving traffic prediction using machine learning as well as real-time and historical data is one area of future effort. Another area is optimizing the timing of traffic signals with connected automobiles.	[15]
2	To introduce a traffic flow forecasting system that makes use of the Internet of Things (IoT), machine	IoT devices for real-time data collection; centralized cloud storage; data preprocessing;	UCI traffic dataset with 2,102 occurrences and 47 characteristics	With a 96% success rate, PSO KNN can forecast traffic flow. With an MSE of 0.00289 as well as an RMSE of 0.0595, the PSO	This suggested approach may be developed to operate in real time and use privacy-preserving strategies to secure the intelligent	[16]

	learning, and feature selection.	PSO for feature selection; KNN, MLP, and Bayes network for classification		KNN algorithm performs well.	transportation system.	
3	Aims to develop a system that can identify and alert about traffic incidents in real-time using deep learning.	Built three models using the Yolov5, Yolor, as well as Faster R-CNN algorithms.	A collection of 8000 annotated images including 36,400 vehicle occurrences derived from CCTV footage, specifically designed for vehicle detection.	The model obtained 98.9% accuracy in detecting fire starting, 83.3% mAP in the Yolov5 method, and 99.2% precision in classifying traffic accidents and their severity.	To enhance and improve the system's ability to obtain the license plate numbers of the automobiles engaged in the incident, the establishment of a license plate localization model will be explored.	[17]
4	To detect, categorize, and monitor road vehicles for effective rural and urban transportation management.	CNN for image segmentation, pyramid pooling for vehicle recognition, Kalman Filter and kernelized filter for vehicle tracking.	German Aerospace Center (DLR) DLR3K, Vehicle Aerial Imaging from a Drone (VAID), and Vehicle Detection in Aerial Imagery (VEDAI)	Vehicle detection rate: 95.78% (VAID), 95.18% (VEDAI), 93.13% (DLR3K)	Conditions such as partial or complete occlusion, shadow from buildings or trees, and similar items were challenges for this investigation.	[18]
5	To propose a method for predicting traffic speed in the near future for metropolitan road networks,	Wasserstein Generative Adversarial Nets (WGAN) are used in the proposed technique to design robust traffic models utilizing generative and discriminative neural networks.	A largescale urban road network in Hangzhou, China.	The model exceeds cutting-edge deep learning algorithms in terms of accuracy and scalability and forecasts short-term traffic speed with effectiveness.	High computing resources are needed for both large-scale implementation and training.	[19]
6	Developing an autonomous system for controlling traffic lights in real-time	Object identification utilizing a machine learning method and image processing using the YOLOv3 framework	Numerous real-time metrics, such as the quantity of vehicles (two- and four-wheelers)Real traffic images and various datasets	81.1% average accuracy was attained in vehicle recognition and efficient green light time estimation using traffic flow data.	Doesn't discuss scalability or computing efficiency for large-scale or multi-junction systems.	[20]

7	To provide an Adaptive Traffic Signal Control (ATSC) framework for intelligent traffic light management that is based on cooperative group-based multi-agent reinforcement learning	Presented CGB-MATSC, a cooperative group-based multi-agent reinforcement learning system.	Considerations for the hypothetical synthetic road network, the cities of Monaco and Harbin	Compared to Fixed time, average waiting time is 42.08% less.	Less scalable and expensive for training	[21]
8	In order to detect traffic accidents, we will use semi-supervised deep learning to handle and analyze massive volumes of data.	Discovered instances of traffic by adapting the multi-modal Generative Adversarial Network model for a semi-supervised setup.	The model is based on four months' worth of data from traffic sensors and social media in the San Francisco Bay Area.	The assessment results unequivocally showed how beneficial the suggested approach is for extracting and categorizing traffic occurrences.	Addressed the fundamental constraints of prior research on merging data analysis of multiple modalities and the absence of labeled data in big data applications.	[22]
9	With the goal of comparing the four DQN methods according to CO2 exhaustion, waiting time, and total automobiles halted.	The following Deep Q-Networks (DQNs) were tested: single-DQN, dueling DQN, double-dueling DQN, and doubly-DQN.	SUMO's randomTrips.py script	Compared to the DQN and double-DQN, the waiting time was reduced by 34.2% and 5.11%, respectively.	Only one intersection environment is taken into consideration.	[23]
10	A density-based adaptive traffic signaling system would allow for better traffic management and optimal control of traffic signals.	Proposed a coordinated system based on DQN, OpenCV, and retrained Yolov3-tiny with traffic density-based signaling techniques.	Primary and secondary data sourced from research papers, journals, websites	The average speed increased by 18% in multi-intersection situations as compared to a static traffic signal system.	Not robust; severe congestion caused performance to decline.	[24]

2.1. Research Gap

Despite the numerous advancements in developing traffic management systems using techniques like YOLO, CNN, and GANs, there remain significant gaps with regard to restricted integration of hybrid models combining techniques for image enhancements and pattern recognitions for urban complex scenarios and underutilized multi-modal sources of data, such as IoT and social media, for providing real-time solutions. The challenges with scaling and computational efficiency have been raised at large applications. Most systems under consideration are based on standalone models that do not scale well and cannot adapt under changes in traffic conditions. Traditional statistical methods fall short in their ability to capture the complexities of spatial-temporal traffic dynamics and variations in weather conditions. In addition, the existing frameworks are also deficient in the integration of strong

deep-learning techniques that combine image enhancement and accurate traffic pattern recognition to handle these complexities effectively. In view of these gaps, this study proposes a hybrid deep-learning framework, integrating GANs for image enhancement and ViTs for accurate traffic pattern analysis to support scalable real-time traffic management solutions. By filling important gaps in optimizing urban traffic systems through improved object detection under challenging conditions and advanced spatial-temporal modeling, the work presented provides a more accurate, adaptable, and efficient means to intelligent traffic management.

3. BACKGROUND

3.1. Generative Adversarial Networks

In the GAN process, two different types of deep learning networks—generative and discriminative—are pitted against one other. Two neural networks, the generator and the discriminator, make up GAN architecture, which is often shown as an abstracted data-flow graph like the one in Fig. 1. The first study [25] teaches the discriminative network to tell the difference between GAN-generated pictures and those from a source database. After being seeded with some random noise, the generative network is trained iteratively to look like the pictures in the discriminative network's training set. In a nutshell, the GAN technique resolved the optimization issue by

$$\min_{\phi_G} \max_{\phi_D} \sum_{i=1}^{n_+} \log f(x_i; \phi_D) + \sum_{j=1}^{n_-} \log (1 - f(g(z_j; \phi_G); \phi_D)) \quad (1)$$

where x_i are images from the original data and z_j are randomly generated images (e.g., each pixel distributed between 0 and 255 uniformly). Let $f(x; \theta_D)$ be a discriminative deep neural network that, given an image, produces a class label and let θ_D denote its parameters. Let $g(z; \theta_G)$ be a generative deep neural network, which given a random input produces an image. The training procedure works as follows. First, we compute the gradient on θ_D to maximize the performance of the discriminative deep neural network. Hence $f(x; \theta_D)$ is able to distinguish between samples from the original data, i.e., x_i , and samples generated from the generative structure, i.e., $x_j^{fake} = g(z_j; \theta_G)$. Second, we compute the gradients on θ_G , so the samples generated from $x_j^{fake} = g(z_j; \theta_G)$ look like a perfect replica of the original data.

When the discriminative network fails to differentiate between the original database samples and the samples produced by the generative network, the operation is terminated.

Figure 1 Representation of the GAN architecture
Source:[26]

3.2 ViT model

A new method for analyzing images, ViTs have emerged in recent years, posing a threat to CNNs' long-standing supremacy [27]. Originally developed for natural language processing (NLP), ViTs use the Transformer architecture to manage image data. Particularly for obtaining global context and long-range interdependence in pictures, this method has worked well. The following elements make up the ViT architecture (Fig.2):

Embedding layer: A series of non-overlapping patches are created from the input picture, and subsequently, each patch is converted into a vector representation. The embedding layer learns the input feature representations using the vector representation of each patch. Next, the Transformer encoder receives its input from the learnt representations.

Transformer encoder: The Transformer encoder consists of multiple layers, each of which is composed of two sub-layers: the multi-head self-attention (MSA) layer and the fully connected feed-forward multilayer perceptron (MLP) layer. The inputs to the encoder are the vector representations of the patches, denoted as z_{l-1} , where $l = 1, 2, \dots, L$ is the layer index, and L is the total number of encoder layers.

One way to define the encoder layer is as:

$$z^l = MLP\left(MSA\left(LN\left(z_{l-1}\right)\right)\right) + z_{l-1}, l = 1 \dots L \quad (2)$$

which stands for fully linked feed-forward multilayer perceptron, MSA for multi-head self-attention layer, and LN for layer normalization.

Applying a normalizing approach to the input to the layer may enhance the network's performance. One such technique is layer normalization. It solves the issue of disappearing gradients in backpropagation by standardizing the input values throughout the feature dimension.

With the normalized input sent via the MSA layer's self-attention mechanism, the network is able to pay closer attention to individual input components and their interdependencies. To create the final output of the layer, the MSA layer's result is applied to the input. To do this, the network makes use of skip connections, which allow data to be sent across layers despite the presence of non-linear activation functions. To keep the gradients intact and prevent the disappearing gradients issue from occurring during backpropagation, this is helpful.

Following the MSA layer, a fully linked feed-forward multilayer perceptron (MLP) is used to process the final output. Using the Gaussian Error Linear Unit (GeLU) activation function, the MLP employs several fully linked layers. By multiplying the inputs by a value between 0 and 1, the GeLU function serves as both an activation and regularizer. In terms of approximating complex functions, the GeLU function outperforms the ReLU functions. Aside from that, vanishing gradients concerns may be alleviated by using GeLU functions.

To the input to the MLP, which is the output from the MSA layer, is then added the MLP's final output. This is the encoder layer's final output. The vanishing gradients issue during backpropagation may be alleviated by performing this procedure, which is also called residual connection.

Each of the Transformer encoder's L encoder layers goes through the same procedure, learning to improve the input's characteristics and producing a more complete representation of the input as it goes.

MLP head: The image representation r is generated by applying layer normalization to the output of the last encoder layer z_L^0 , which is acquired by:

$$r = LN\left(z_L^0\right) \quad (3)$$

After then, an MLP head receives the picture representation r and uses it to categorize the topics. The activation function employed by the MLP head, which is a single hidden layer, is the sigmoid function.

Figure 2 Vision Transformer ViT Architecture
Source:[28]

4. METHODOLOGY

This research details a methodical strategy for creating hybrid deep learning models for smart traffic systems' real-time image processing frameworks. Gathering data, cleaning it up, building a model, testing it, and finally optimizing it in real time are all part of the technique. It will combine GANs for enhancing images and ViTs for traffic pattern recognition in order to increase accuracy and robustness in dynamic traffic environments. The state-of-the-art image processing technique has been used to enhance the quality of traffic images for improved model performance. It has been designed with the methodology of scalability and efficiency, which is very much required for real-time applications in urban settings. Our suggested architecture for developing smart traffic systems with real-time picture processing is shown in Algorithm 1 (Fig. 3).

4.1. Data Collection

The dataset used for this study is the Traffic-Net from Kaggle, where one can obtain the real-time images of traffic, plus labels on other objects, for example, cars, pedestrians, or other related entities in the process of traffic flow. These objects will provide a basis for testing and training this new proposed hybrid model intended for smart traffic systems. Diverse images regarding traffic help ensure robust training and the capacity of a model to recognize dynamic real-time traffic scenarios and conditions.

The Traffic-Net dataset is available for download at:

<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/umairshahpirzada/traffic-net>

4.2. Data Preprocessing:

The process of data preprocessing ensures that a dataset is clean and consistent for proper training of the deep learning models. For this research, there were several preprocessing steps applied.

- **Image Resizing:** Resize all images to a standard dimension that is appropriate for model training (e.g., 256x256 or 512x512 pixels).
- **Data Augmentation:** Employ data augmentation using rotation, flip, adjust the brightness and zoom to create traffic variability so the model could also be strong to such types of variability.
- **Normalization:** Normalize pixel values to the range [0, 1] to improve convergence during training.

4.3. Training-test Split

This model training and testing data set has been divided into two equal halves.

- **Training Set (80%):** It is the training subset. The model learns from data and adjusts parameters in order to minimize the loss function. Hyperparameter optimization involves adjusting the model's parameters based on the results from the training set.
- **Testing Set (20%):** This is unseen data to which the model is never exposed in the training process. The testing set will help prove how good the model is and generalizes to the data unseen and ensures predictions are proper and sound enough for real applications by the model.

5. MODEL BUILDING

For data creation, the hybrid architecture uses Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), while for feature extraction and classification, it uses Vision Transformers (ViTs). GANs augment the dataset by adding synthetic traffic images, thus allowing increasing diversity and preventing class imbalances, while applying ViTs efficiently for feature extraction and classification.

5.1. GAN Architecture

The generator transfers the high-resolution traffic picture to a random noise vector that is sampled from a normal distribution. For upsampling, the generator used a fully connected layer followed by convolutional transpose layers. LeakyReLU is applied in the middle layers, while Tanh was used in the output layer. Batch normalization has been used for stabilizing training. The discriminator uses convolutional layers to extract spatial characteristics from both real and synthetic pictures, and then uses fully connected layers to determine whether the input is genuine or artificial. The discriminator's goal is to differentiate real images from generated ones.

The loss functions used are based on Wasserstein GAN with Gradient Penalty (WGAN-GP) to avoid mode collapse:

$$\begin{aligned} L_D &= E[D(x_{real})] - E[D(x_{fake})] + \lambda.GP \\ L_G &= -E[D(x_{fake})] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where L_D and L_G are the losses for the discriminator and generator, respectively, and GP represents the gradient penalty.

5.2. ViT Architecture

ViT processes the images of traffic by dividing them into fixed-sized patches (for example, 16×16). Each patch is flattened and projected through a linear embedding layer. Positional embeddings are added for retaining spatial information. The transformer encoder applies the MHSA for getting the relationship across patches and applies FFN for further processing. Layer normalization and residual connections make sure it is stable. The encoder produces a collection of feature representations as its output.

A fully linked layer and a softmax activation make up the classification head, which is responsible for classifying traffic conditions using the token:

$$P(class) = \text{Soft max}(FC([CLS])) \quad (5)$$

where $P(class)$ is the probability distribution over the classes, and FC represents the fully connected layer.

This hybrid architecture leverages GANs for data augmentation and ViTs for robust classification, enabling accurate traffic image generation and classification.

5.3. Model evaluation

The model's performance is evaluated using the test dataset (20%) that was not part of the training process. Key performance metrics include:

- **Accuracy:** It is the method most frequently used to assess classification algorithms. Its definition is the proportion of correctly identified data items to all observations. It is simple to measure the classifier's accuracy rate of making accurate predictions.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{S} \quad (6)$$

- **Precision:** The ratio of true positive predictions to the total number of positive predictions made by the model is called precision. To put it simply, it is:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (7)$$

where FP stands for False Positive and TP for True Positive.

- **Recall:** A model's recall indicates how well it can identify important instances in the dataset. The calculation is:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (8)$$

FN stands for the number of false negatives.

- **F1-Score:** An integrated statistic, the F1 Score equalizes recall and accuracy by taking their harmonic means. It is determined by:

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (9)$$

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, the results and analysis of the Hybrid GAN & ViT Model performance are presented regarding real-time traffic event classification as compared to individual models, which include GAN, ViT, and YOLOv8. This assessment is conducted on the TrafficNet dataset that contains traffic-related events like accidents, heavy congestion, fire incidents, and light traffic.

Figure 3 Algorithm for Hybrid DL model for Smart Traffic System

6.1. Confusion Matrix

Testing on the TrafficNet dataset reveals that the Hybrid GAN & ViT Model performs better, with 98.63% accuracy, 98.13% recall, and 98.43% F1-score. This shows the successful real-time implementation, as the correct identification of events in the road segment is enabled by the benefits of these architectures. With its GAN model, we get a 94.63% success rate. This model proves its validity as a standalone by showing comparisons to the aforementioned models in terms of accuracy, recall, and F1-score. The accuracy it achieves is 92.38%. Efficacy-wise, YOLOv8 is less productive. Its results yield a mere 90.13% of accuracy. For precision, recall, and F1-score metrics, a reduced value has been observed. The results depict how the hybrid model improves the classifiers' performance, making it the most reliable model for this classification task.

6.2. ROC Curve

Figure 8: ROC curve of Hybrid GAN and ViT model

Figure 9: ROC curve of GAN model

Figure 10: ROC curve of ViT model

Figure 11: ROC curve of YOLOv8 model

ROC curves of all four models are shown, that is, Hybrid Model, GAN, ViT, and YOLOv8 depicting their classification efficacy. The AUC of Hybrid Model is 1.00, meaning no misclassification; the AUC of the GAN model is 0.96, that is, effective class discrimination. The ViT Model showed excellent performance with an AUC of 0.95, indicating that it has the best classification capability. On the other hand, the YOLOv8 Model shows considerable predictive effectiveness as it has an AUC of 0.93, which is relatively smaller compared to that of the GAN and ViT models. The Hybrid Model is much better than the rest. However, the GAN, ViT, and YOLOv8 models have better classification effectiveness. The AUC values are not so different.

6.3. Performance Metrics

Figure 12: Bar plot for evaluation

The GAN, ViT, YOLOv8, and Hybrid GAN & ViT models' relative performances across all assessment criteria are shown in the bar chart. On every measure, the results are in favor of the Hybrid GAN and ViT Model. Accuracy, recall, and F1-score have all been enhanced, bringing the model up to 0.98. The GAN model shows outstanding performance against all the benchmarks and shows elevated classification efficiencies. Experiments conducted with the ViT and YOLOv8 models have been inconsistent. The latter has shown low efficacy and, of all the benchmark test datasets applied, produced the worst results. These experiments definitively prove that the Hybrid model proposed, in which GAN is integrated into the ViT model, leverages the inbuilt strengths of both architectures.

6.4. Discussion

The research work emphasizes the crucial complexity of the machine learning solution required for the real-time traffic event classification process. The dataset used for the classification of events in the network will be the TrafficNet, which encompasses accidents of vehicles, various conditions in traffic, and fire incidents. Of the mentioned above, Hybrid GAN & ViT Model is the most reliable one that integrates two of the strongest generative data augmentation methods from GANs with Vision Transformers' spatial feature extraction ability. The Hybrid GAN and ViT Model has excellent performance with evaluation metrics. With 98.63% accuracy, 98.63 precision, 98.13 recall, and 98.43 F1-score, it is rather impressive. A faultless performance in traffic event classification will be shown by a ROC-AUC value of 1.00.

On the other hand, GAN and ViT models obtain 94.63 and 92.38, while the performance of the YOLOv8 model comes out to be around 90.13%. All the observations concluded that these hybrid models combined the strength of other architectures and improved the performance.

This product is imperative for fast response decision-making within intelligent traffic systems; it is enabling efficient flow, real-time incident detection and response, and optimizing emergency situations. This research contributes to a gold standard for future studies by taking new, innovative methodologies of deep learning and applying them directly to real problems. The proposed hybrid model displays outstanding performance concerning the selected task and introduces an innovative solution in setting up sound, scalable, infrastructure globally on intelligent traffic systems.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This study confirms that Hybrid GAN and the ViT Model are adept to tackle all challenges of the real-time classification problem of traffic events. The effective integration of GAN generative capabilities with Vision Transformers' feature extraction abilities allows the model to exhibit notable performance metrics over all benchmarks. It thus outperforms all competing models, including standalone GAN, ViT, and YOLOv8. This is a marked step forward for traffic management technologies, allowing monitoring of real-time traffic, real-time

incident detection, and emergency responses. This will set a base for future achievements in machine learning and pragmatic applications that may further underpin global traffic systems: more intelligent, secure, and adaptive.

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